

Custom-built wireless sensor networks to monitor soil moisture

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Abstract

The temporal change of soil moisture storage is one of the most critical pieces of information required for efficient irrigation management. Measurement of soil moisture in the past was very expensive and accounting for spatial variability was largely impractical. Recent technological developments now make it possible to monitor soil moisture in near real time using wireless sensor networks. This paper presents a successful application of custom-built wireless mesh sensor networks based on DigiMesh protocol, a proprietary technology developed by Digi International Inc. to monitor spatial distribution of soil moisture in near real time. Our system is designed to transport the measured data from wireless sensor networks in the field to cloud data base servers over cellular networks or Iridium satellites. Data are then processed to make them available on smart phone-compatible web browsers in near real time to help practitioners plan their precision irrigation scheduling.

Background

Precision irrigation scheduling derived from near real time soil moisture data at targeted positions is the key to efficient farm management. Use of predictive models to estimate soil water status demands a wide range of environmental, crop and soil data that are difficult to measure accurately. Although these numerical models were developed to obey the law of physics and mathematics, the accuracy of the predictive results is only as good as the accuracy of the parameters fed into these models. As instruments used in the past to measure soil moisture data were bulky and expensive to use in large numbers, a predictive modelling approach has been a common choice to estimate soil moisture for irrigation scheduling. However, recent advances in wireless technology using low-power digital radios operating in licence-free frequency bands allow direct measurement of soil moisture, which is more appealing to practitioners than the predictive modelling approach. This is because it requires just a few precise soil moisture measurements from targeted positions compared with measuring large numbers of climatic, crop, and soil variables to use predictive models. There are a few wireless technologies available for building your own or purchasing off the shelf wireless sensor networks. Limitations on network expandability of ZigBee WSN technology, which is the most common and international standard protocol developed for building WSN networks, make it less appealing for monitoring soil moisture in the agricultural environment. We therefore designed, built, and successfully tested, customised sensor networks using DigiMesh protocol, which, while of non-international standard, has the added advantages of simplicity, reliability, and expandability.

Method

Mesh networks

Mesh networks are capable of interconnecting sensor nodes with each other using multiple pathways that are updated and optimized dynamically, allowing sensor nodes to self-discover and self-heal to derive the most energy-efficient pathways to relay data to the base station or gateway.

ZigBee mesh networks

ZigBee is a wireless technology developed as an open global standard to create low-cost, low-power wireless M2M networks. The ZigBee standard operates on the IEEE 802.15.4 physical radio specification in unlicensed bands including 2.4GHz, 900MHz and 868MHz (Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers, IEEE). Over 300 leading semiconductor manufacturers, technology firms, OEMs, and service companies are members of the ZigBee Alliance. Because it is an international standard, sensors from different ZigBee alliances are easily interchangeable in a ZigBee sensor network and ZigBee is therefore a popular choice for monitoring sensor networks (Perera, 2010). ZigBee protocols define three types of nodes – Coordinators, Routers and End Nodes – requiring one Coordinator per one network (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Topology of ZigBee mesh network.
End devices are not able to route data

End devices are low-power, sleep-enabled devices that cannot relay data to the coordinator via other devices in the network. This inability of end devices to relay data is the major disadvantage of ZigBee protocols because main-powered additional routers capable of relaying data to other devices are essential to expand the sensor networks.

DigiMesh mesh networks

In contrast to the ZigBee networks, which have three node types, the DigiMesh networks have only one type of node, which is capable of acting as a coordinator, router or end device (Fig. 2) This will allow the formation of expandable, simpler and more reliable mesh networks as routers may come and go through interference and damage in open agricultural environments. A comprehensive description of the two systems is given in Qandour (2012) and Sensors on Line (2008).

Figure 2. Topology of DigiMesh sensor network.
All nodes are able to route data

Sleeping routers

Given that DigiMesh allows all nodes, including the Coordinator, to sleep, thereby increasing battery life, through reduced power consumption, the nodes can be battery powered. Currently, ZigBee allows only End Devices to sleep but not Routers or Coordinators. The sleeping of any sensor node is achieved by time synchronisation. The major advantage of the DigiMesh networks is that it eliminates the single point failure associated with relying on a coordinator. DigiMesh establishes time synchronisation through a nomination and election process, enabling the network to operate autonomously. After time synchronisation, all sensor nodes wakeup in unison, exchange data, and go back to sleep. Simplicity, reliability, and expandability are the main reasons we have selected DigiMesh technology to create our wireless sensor network.

Current systems: getting data to cloud and web servers.

The ultimate goal of a wireless sensor network is to transport the measured data to web servers and make them available on smart phones and compatible web browsers over the internet using state-of-the-art data visualisation tools. Two common methods are available to transport data to web servers: Option 1: a mesh sensor network is used to gather data at a base station (Gateway) that is linked to the internet via cellular network; or Option 2: each sensor node is linked to the internet via a cellular network, creating a mesh sensor network on the cellular network. However, we selected Option 1 because Option 2 becomes very expensive as the number of sensor nodes in the sensor network increases, as each node requires a dedicated SIM card and cellular connection with the data package. Our method uses Option 1 to monitor soil moisture in farms where cellular coverage is very weak and patchy, by locating the gateway at a suitable point where, using a high-gain Yagi antenna, it can be connected to a cell tower over 40 km away.

Building a customised wireless soil moisture sensor network

The sensor network configuration depends on the number of monitoring locations, which is determined by the number of soil management zones on the farm. EM mapping is popular among growers and is used to classify different soil zones (e.g. Hedley & Yule, 2009). For example, a Geonics electromagnetic EM38[®] sensor with on-board data logger, RTK-DGPS and field computer is dragged behind an all-terrain vehicle (ATV) to collect georeferenced soil electrical conductivity EC (mS/m) data (e.g. Hedley & Yule, 2009). Adequate soil sampling positions are selected to investigate the full range of soil EC values by taking intact soil cores at each point from three soil depths (e.g. 0–0.2 m, 0.2–0.4 m, and 0.4–0.6 m) to assess available water-holding capacity (AWC) (Hedley & Yule, 2009). The sampling depths are selected to reflect the majority of the root zone from which water is extracted by plants. The results are used to define irrigation management zones, based on soil AWC differences.

Hardware for wireless sensor nodes

Digi International Inc. does not provide complete wireless sensor network solutions for monitoring sensors in an agricultural environment. Instead, they provide software IDE (Integrated Development Environment) and hardware tools to help develop your own wireless mesh networks using their low-power radios modules and cellular gateways. A range of DigiMesh radio modules covering licenced free frequency bands 2.4GHz, 900 MHz, and 868MHz are available depending on the country's radio spectrum management laws. We have selected 2.4GHz radio modules with 60mW, DSSS (Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum), which are allowed in New Zealand under free licence (General User Radio Licence for Short Range Devices) <https://gazette.govt.nz/notice/id/2017-go415>.

The complete soil moisture monitoring setup is shown in Figure 3. Replicated wireless sensor nodes are installed in selected soil zones. Two soil moisture sensors are installed at each monitoring location at two depths to monitor the root zone. To increase mesh network reliability it is important to install the wireless sensor nodes in such a way that one node could see at least two other nodes. This will increase the robustness of the wireless mesh network by increasing the chances of self-healing and self-discovery. As all wireless nodes in the DigiMesh network are capable of relaying data, this arrangement also helps expand the wireless network reliably.

The heart of a wireless sensor node is the XBee radio, (Digi.com, 2017) for data communication, and a PIC18f25k20 microcontroller to interface different type of sensors to the radio. Although the XBee radio itself has the ability to measure and send data without the help of a micro controller, a PIC18F25K20 was incorporated into the sensor node to accommodate a range of sensors with both digital (SDI-12) and analogue (SM300, ML3) data communication interfaces.

Figure 3. Wireless mesh sensor network and data visualisation system, which has been designed to accommodate sensors with different communication interfaces

The coordinator and the wireless sensor node radios with the same network address form a personal area network. In our DigiMesh sensor networks all nodes wake up in unison, exchange data, synchronise the clocks, and go back to sleep. Wake up and sleep times can be varied remotely from a few minutes to one day.

Data visualisation

Currently, the most preferred way of making field data available to the practitioners is via eye-catching simple data visualisation tools compatible with smart phones. We have developed tools (using Fusion Charts, a commercially available charting tool that has been customised using PHP software running on a dedicated web server hosted on a commercial service provider) to stream near real time data over the internet to standard web browsers on desk tops as well as on smart phones.

Irrigation map

This is the simplest way of presenting the irrigation requirement in different soil zones (Fig. 4). The volume of cylinders represents the maximum plant-available water capacity and the empty portion simply shows the deficit. We allow the practitioner to decide the amount of irrigation to apply. This pictorial visualisation of irrigation requirements is quite popular among practitioners as the visualisation is very intuitive.

Time series of soil moisture data

Soil moisture data are also presented as combinations of time series with re-fill and field capacity lines. This allows practitioners to manage irrigation strategies to minimize the drainage and plant water stress. The screen shot of the web page in Figure 3 shows how such irrigation management is achieved by keeping the soil moisture time series in between refill and field capacity lines. Figure 4 shows soil moisture as time series with irrigation and rainfall without the control lines.

Figure 4. Soil moisture at 20- and 40-cm depths in 3 soil zones, A, B & C (arable site, Hawke's Bay, New Zealand). Screen shot of the Irrigation map web page showing irrigation requirements of different soil zones. Total volumes of the cylinders represent the maximum plant available water capacities.

Conclusions

We have provided an example of a customised wireless soil-moisture sensor network installed into an irrigated field that sends data via a cloud-based database to a smart phone app and webpage. The aim is to provide a simple tool for land managers to inform them when, where, and how much irrigation needs to be applied at any one time.

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References

- Digi.com 2017. https://www.digi.com/pdf/ds_xbeemultipointmodules.pdf (accessed 06.09.17).
- Hedley C, Yule I 2009. Soil water status mapping and two variable-rate irrigation scenarios. *Journal of Precision Agriculture* 10: 342–355.
- Perera A 2010. Zigbee wireless soil moisture sensor design for vineyard management system. Masters thesis, Auckland University of Technology, New Zealand.
- Qandour A 2012. Application framework for wireless sensor networks. Theses: Doctorates and Masters, Edith Cowan University, Australia.
- Sensors on Line 2008. <http://www.sensormag.com/components/what-a-mesh-part-2-networking-architectures-and-protocols> (accessed 09.06.17).